

FACTORS AND CONDITIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS OF A MODERN TEACHER

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Abstract: Modernization of higher education institutions and the educational process in them, increasing the quality monitoring of the system of training pedagogic specialists, equipping modern teachers with modern professional knowledge, qualifications and skills, in relation to the professional and pedagogical skills of modern teachers formation of acmeological motivation is one of the important tasks in the process of formation of professional training of pedagogues.

Keywords: equipping modern teachers with modern professional knowledge, qualifications and skills, mastering skills and qualifications, professional and pedagogical skills of a modern teacher

The concept of a profession is an occupation that requires special training, a person constantly experiences and serves as a source of livelihood. The profession unites people engaged in the same activity, and certain relations and moral norms are established within this activity.

E.A. In his studies, Klimov states that "Profession is a necessary and valuable field for society, which requires physical and mental strength from a person.

V.G. Makushin says that the profession is an activity with the help of which a person participates in the life of society and serves as the main source of material means for his life.

Summarizing the existing definitions, it can be concluded as follows: "Profession is the main form of labor activity, in order to perform it, a person must have certain knowledge, skills and abilities, special abilities and developed important professional qualities."

Specialization is a complex of special knowledge, skills and abilities acquired through professional education and training, which are necessary for performing a certain type of activity within this or that profession.

Thus, specialization is directed to personal achievements within the profession or to achieving general results through specific situations.

Professional preparation of a specialist is one of the conditions for the

effectiveness of a modern teacher's professional and pedagogical skills.

The famous Russian psychologist I.K. According to Platonov, "professional training is the subjective state of a person who believes that he is able and prepared to perform the necessary professional-pedagogical skills of a modern teacher and strives to perform them."

E. Seytkhalilov, B. Rakhimov and N. Azizkhodjaeva explain that "professional training is the process of acquiring theoretical knowledge, skills and abilities that allow a person to engage in the professional and pedagogical skills of a modern teacher."

R. Ishmuhamedov, A. Abdugadirov and A. Pardaev emphasize that the basis of professional training should reflect "psychological, psychophysiological, physical and scientific-theoretical and practical training of a modern teacher".

Based on the opinions of the authors, the concept of "professional training" can be defined as follows:

Professional training is the level of physiological, psychological and physical preparation of a modern teacher for carrying out professional-pedagogical skills on the basis of special theoretical knowledge, practical skills and qualifications, as well as mastering spiritual and moral qualities.

Formation of professional training - formation of special theoretical knowledge, practical skills and qualifications, as well as spiritual and moral qualities in a person based on the requirements of DTS. is a preparation process.

Development of professional and pedagogical skills of a modern teacher means mastering and individualization of professional and pedagogical skills of a modern teacher.

It is known that one of the important tasks of every higher education institution is to ensure that first-year modern teachers have a positive adaptation to the new system of education, new social relations, and successfully master the status of modern teachers.

When adapting modern teachers to the conditions of a higher education institution, it is necessary to highlight the following aspects:

- 3) the adaptation process of modern teachers has a complex dynamic and requires the mutual harmony of social and personal values;
- 4) the first and in some cases the second year of study for modern teachers is accompanied by difficult situations;
- 5) in the process of studying at a higher educational institution, modern teachers develop a sense of self-awareness, the development of the system of valuable relations with the environment and existence continues;

- 6) modern teachers develop basic educational principles;
- 7) modern teaching years have an organizational, methodical and psychological description and are the most important stage of a person's professional and personal adaptation.

In fact, professional adaptation is considered a complex and multifaceted process, based on which the opportunities that ensure successful work in a specific profession, the orientation of the person, professional knowledge, skills, qualifications and professional qualities, work experience are also the main criteria. appears.

We know that a person is an active object and subject of the educational process, and the activity of a modern teacher in the process of professional-pedagogical skills is determined by his direction.

While researching the problem of personality orientation, S.L. Rubinstein expresses it in terms of needs, interests, ideals, beliefs, priority motives of activity and behavior, and worldviews.

Psychological scientists L.I. Bojovich and R.S. Nemov interprets that personality orientation is a system and sum of motives.

Professional orientation is a unique form of personal orientation, which is reflected in the influence of motives and needs.

In the literature on pedagogic and professional education, attention is paid to the concept of "professional orientation" meaning the following content: 1) "Professional orientation" - a person's ability, interests, need and firm belief in a specific type of activity (A.B. Seyteshev); 2) "Professional orientation" - leadership in personal qualities of connection between career choice, interest, firm confidence and career choice motives (N.K. Stepankova).

In the works of some researchers, there are attempts to reveal the essence of the concept of "orientation to the pedagogical profession", taking into account the direct orientation of a person to the professional and pedagogical skills of a modern teacher. Including:

- 1) "Pedagogical profession orientation" - a person's "interest in the pedagogical profession and passion for this type of activity" (N.V. Kuzmina);
- 2) "Orientation towards the pedagogical profession" - attitude towards children, enthusiasm for pedagogical work, ability of pedagogical observation.

As can be seen from the terminological analysis, the concept of "orientation towards the pedagogical profession" mainly reflects the fact that the choice of profession affects the professional development of a person under the active influence of motives.

The concept of motive is interpreted in psychological literature (lat. movere - to move) as a motivating reason for activities related to the satisfaction of certain needs.

Choosing a profession is a complex and motivating process, and the right choice of a person's profession leads to a person's satisfaction with life and a clear determination of his social status.

Research scientist E.S. Chugunova has developed a classification of motivations for choosing a workplace and a profession, and defines the motivations for choosing a profession, which reflect the reasons for the professional and pedagogical skills of any modern teacher, as follows:

- dominant (predominance of interest in the profession);
- related to the situation (realization of the conditions that have always interested a person);
- conformist;
- other professional motivations (with the advice of the social world close to him, i.e. relatives, friends and acquaintances).

A.K. Baymetov studies the motivations for striving for pedagogical activity and combines the main ones:

- a) motive of inevitability (duty);
- b) the interestingness of the taught subjects and attracting attention;
- c) communicating with children.

According to the studied sources, the types of motivation affect the direction and character of professional training of modern teachers.

In this regard, N.V. Kuzmina emphasizes that the motives of a person for the pedagogical profession are in three different cases:

- 1) real pedagogical;
- 2) officially pedagogical;
- 3) false pedagogical direction.

The first condition in the organization of pedagogical activity, that is, the real pedagogical direction, acquires a positive character and helps to achieve the acmeological level in pedagogical activity. In the organization of pedagogical activity, only the first-rate pedagogical training helps to achieve high results. The main motive of the real pedagogical orientation is the interest in pedagogical activity.

In the process of our pedagogical observation and when we studied the main reasons why modern teachers chose the teaching profession, 33% of the respondent-modern teachers chose the teaching profession by choice, 31.2% It

turned out that 35.4% chose this educational institution in order to continue their education in pedagogical higher education institutions based on their interest in a particular subject and their parents' recommendations. However, the high level of financial security of the teaching profession compared to other professions indicates that the stereotypes formed by parents have not left their influence on the youth.

We think that the motivations for choosing a profession, professional direction, and the manifestation of life goals in different directions will affect the low level of professional adaptation or prolong it for a long time. .

Although the motives of choosing a profession are more clearly observed in the direction of professional and pedagogical skills of a modern teacher, it should be noted that they alone cannot play a leading role in the development of professional training. Because the existing physical, mental and spiritual capabilities of a person are proportional to the level of the professional-pedagogical skill requirements of the selected modern teacher, which helps the modern teacher to adapt to the normal development of the professional-pedagogical skill environment and the development of reflection.

Professional opportunities reflect the objective conditions of a certain activity related to the individual's will.

Usually, in adapting modern teachers to the professional and pedagogical skills of a modern teacher, it is considered appropriate to approach them based on their objective capabilities, to identify the individual's capabilities to the requirements of the chosen profession and activity. For example, when choosing a teaching profession, it is not only the love of this profession, the desire to communicate with children, but also the physical, psychological and social requirements of the professional-pedagogical skills of a modern teacher that are within his capabilities, professional knowledge, skills and vision. helps to acquire skills.

Therefore, special attention should be paid to the theoretical justification of these aspects of the modern teacher's professional and pedagogical skills and to the development of the professional capabilities of modern teachers.

The determination of the professional knowledge to be mastered by modern teachers based on the content of the qualification requirements for the quality level of a specialist is an important criterion that determines the effectiveness of the process of developing the professional and pedagogical skills of a modern teacher.

In the Classifier, which incorporates the quality requirements for modern

teachers, modern teachers work in general education schools, academic lyceums, vocational colleges, and they organize the educational process within their specialty, It is determined that students should have the necessary professional knowledge, skills and abilities to be able to fairly assess and control the level of knowledge.

In our opinion, thoughts about the uniqueness of a person represent the external aspects of individuality. Individuality is the distinction of a person from the animal and social world.

The source of his life and professional-pedagogical skills is embodied in the individuality of a person. A person with a developed individuality fully relies on his own strength, and thus he appears as a free and independent person.

Comparative analysis of individuality and person makes it possible to clarify the relationship between man and society (community and man).

So, in conclusion, the individuality of a person, professional qualities, knowledge, skills and system of qualifications serve as one of the important factors in the professional-pedagogical skill of a modern teacher.

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